

EVALUATION OF EFFECT OF ECDM PROCESS PARAMETERS ON INCONEL 625 PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS USING ENTROPY-TOPSIS

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Abstract

The present research focuses on the multi-objective optimization of electrochemical drilling machining (ECDM) of Inconel 625 using a Taguchi-based Entropy-TOPSIS approach. Unlike conventional studies that primarily consider material removal rate (MRR) and surface roughness (Ra), this investigation uniquely incorporates additional geometric accuracy measures such as overcut, form, and orientation tolerance errors. The integrated optimization framework successfully yielded a single optimal parameter setting of feed rate of 0.20 mm/min, flow rate of 0.75 L/min, and electrolyte concentration of 10% to achieve improved multi performance machining characteristics.

The Taguchi analysis revealed that feed rate (F) and flow rate (Q) exhibit non monotonic effects, whereas electrolyte concentration (C) shows a clear monotonic decreasing trend, suggesting that F and Q should be adjusted around moderate levels while maintaining a lower C to enhance closeness coefficient ($C_i +$) performance. ANOVA results validated the statistical model with a high level of significance ($P = 0.000$), identifying F and Q as the most influential parameters, along with their strong interaction effect ($F \times Q$). Although factor C alone was statistically insignificant, its interaction with Q was found to be meaningful. The developed regression model was confirmed to be reliable with high coefficient of determination values ($R^2 = 94.23\%$ and $R^2(\text{adj}) = 91.18\%$). Overall, the findings establish that the Taguchi-based Entropy TOPSIS method is a robust and effective approach for achieving optimal electrochemical drilling performance in Inconel 625, making it a valuable tool for addressing complex multi-response optimization problems in advanced machining applications.

Keywords: Electrochemical Drilling Machining (ECDM), TOPSIS, Material Removal Rate (MRR), Surface Roughness (Ra), Overcut (OC), Circularity Error (CE) and Perpendicularity error (PE).

1. Introduction

In modern engineering industries, the selection of appropriate materials and the choice of machining techniques play a decisive role in determining the performance, safety, and durability of manufactured components. With the rapid advancement of technology, the demand for high-strength alloys and advanced manufacturing methods has been increasing across aerospace, nuclear, chemical, and marine sectors. Components used in these industries are often subjected to extreme operating conditions such as high temperature, pressure, corrosive environments, and mechanical stresses. Therefore, materials that can withstand such harsh conditions without losing their strength or stability are indispensable. One such group of materials is the Inconel family of nickel-based superalloys. Inconel alloys have earned a reputation for exceptional mechanical properties, corrosion resistance, and stability at elevated temperatures. Their ability to retain strength and resist oxidation makes them essential in applications where reliability and safety are paramount. However, these same properties that make Inconel useful also make it difficult to machine by conventional techniques. High cutting forces, severe tool wear, and poor surface finish are common challenges encountered when machining Inconel with traditional processes such as turning, milling, and drilling. To address these limitations, industries and researchers have turned toward non-traditional machining processes. Among these,

Electrochemical Machining (ECM) has emerged as one of the most effective techniques for processing Inconel alloys. ECM operates on the principle of electrolysis and removes material by controlled anodic dissolution, ensuring stress-free, precise, and efficient machining without tool wear.

Working Principle of ECM: In essence, the electrochemical machining process relies on Faraday's law of electrolysis. In Faraday's law of electrolysis, when two electrodes are placed in an electrolyte, an anode (+ve) and a cathode (-ve), the mass of metal that is deposited on the cathode corresponding to the anode is directly proportional to the potential difference between them. The process of electrochemical machining begins with the tool being moved closer to the workpiece. The workpiece and tool are immersed in an electrolyte with a very small gap between them. When a direct current (DC) potential difference is applied, the tool behaves as a cathode, and the workpiece acts as an anode. The process of removing metal from the workpiece begins once the electrolysis condition is met. According to the tool's shape, metal removal occurs. The flow of electrolytes causes the material to be removed from the workpiece and settle down as a slug. After that, the electrolyte goes through filtration. During this process, the electrolyte is centrifuged to remove the slugs. After that, any additional impurities are removed through a filter. In the event of a rise in electrolyte pressure, the pressure valve directly diverts the flow to the tank.

2. Methodology

In modern manufacturing and research environments, industries are constantly aiming to achieve higher product quality, improved process efficiency, and cost reduction. However, real-world processes are influenced by several factors, some of which are controllable (such as machine parameters, tool geometry, feed rate, and voltage) and some of which are uncontrollable (such as temperature, vibrations, and material inconsistencies). To achieve optimum results, systematic approaches are required to identify significant parameters, study their effects, and optimize them for desired outcomes. Two of the most widely used statistical and experimental design approaches in engineering research are the Taguchi Method and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). These methods are complementary: Taguchi helps in identifying the optimal set of process parameters through orthogonal arrays and signal-to-noise ratio analysis, while ANOVA validates the statistical significance of the results and quantifies the percentage contribution of each factor. The present research adopts a systematic and integrated experimental-analytical framework to optimize the Electrochemical Drilling Machining (ECDM) parameters for Inconel 625 using the Taguchi-Entropy-TOPSIS approach. The methodology is structured to ensure statistical reliability, experimental accuracy, and decision-making efficiency across multiple performance criteria. The study encompasses several interlinked phases: experimental design using the Taguchi method, data acquisition, analysis through the Entropy weighting method, multi-criteria optimization using TOPSIS, and statistical validation using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

1. Experimental Framework and Objectives:

The primary goal of this study is to determine the optimal combination of feed rate (F), electrolyte flow rate (Q), and electrolyte concentration (C) that can simultaneously improve multiple output characteristics — Material Removal Rate (MRR), Surface Roughness (Ra), Overcut (OC), Circularity Error (CE), and Perpendicularity Error (PE). Since these responses often exhibit conflicting trends (for example, higher MRR may worsen surface finish), a multi-response optimization strategy is essential.

The experimental plan was implemented using the ELECHEM TECHNIK Electrochemical Drilling Machine, operating at a constant 24 V. The setup included a machining chamber, electrolyte circulation pump, control panel, and current-sensing safety circuit to prevent tool damage. A hollow cylindrical electrode allowed the sodium chloride (NaCl) electrolyte to flow through the machining zone, facilitating controlled electrochemical dissolution.

The work material — Inconel 625, known for its high strength and corrosion resistance — was selected because of its industrial importance and machining challenges. Its chemical composition (Nickel balance, 20–23% Chromium, 8–10% Molybdenum, 0.50% Iron, and trace elements) makes it ideal for assessing the ECDM process's precision and efficiency.

2. Taguchi Experimental Design:

The Taguchi Method, a robust statistical tool for design of experiments (DOE), was employed to minimize experimental runs while maximizing information extraction. Taguchi's orthogonal array (OA) concept was used to analyze the influence of multiple parameters efficiently. An L27 OA was selected since three control factors (F, Q, and C) each had three levels.

The levels for each parameter were:

- Feed rate (F): 0.15, 0.20, 0.25 mm/min
- Flow rate (Q): 0.5, 0.75, 1.0 L/min
- Electrolyte concentration (C): 10%, 15%, 20%

This design resulted in 27 unique experimental trials, each corresponding to a specific combination of parameters. Each trial produced quantitative data for all five performance metrics.

3. Measurement of Responses:

After each ECDM operation, the machined samples were evaluated using high-precision instruments:

- Material Removal Rate (MRR) was calculated by measuring the difference in workpiece weight before and after machining, divided by the machining time.
- Surface Roughness (Ra) was measured using a Kosaka Surf Coder SE1200, offering a resolution of 0.08 μm .
- Geometrical errors — Overcut (OC), Circularity Error (CE), and Perpendicularity Error (PE) — were determined using a Helmel Coordinate Measuring Machine (CMM) (Model 216–142).

These measurements were compiled to form a decision matrix, which served as the foundation for the Entropy–TOPSIS optimization process.

4. Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) Framework:

In real-world manufacturing, no single parameter set can optimize all responses simultaneously. Therefore, a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) technique is essential. The Entropy–TOPSIS hybrid approach was employed because it provides objective weighting (through Entropy) and reliable ranking (through TOPSIS) of alternatives.

4.1 Entropy Weight Calculation

The Entropy Method determines the relative importance (weights) of each performance criterion based on the information provided by the data itself — avoiding subjective bias.

Steps included:

1. Normalization of data to convert responses into a dimensionless scale, allowing fair comparison across different units (e.g., μm , mm, g/min).
2. Entropy value computation (E_j), representing the disorder or information content in each criterion.
3. Degree of diversification ($D_j = 1 - E_j$) was derived, giving more importance to criteria with higher variability.
4. Weight assignment (W_j) — the final weights were calculated by dividing each diversification value by the sum of all diversifications.

4.2 TOPSIS Optimization

The Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) ranks all alternatives based on their geometric proximity to an ideal solution.

Steps involved:

1. Weighted Normalization: Each normalized criterion was multiplied by its respective weight to form the weighted normalized matrix.
2. Identification of Ideal Solutions:
 - Positive Ideal Solution (PIS): Best achievable performance (e.g., maximum MRR, minimum Ra, OC, CE, PE).
 - Negative Ideal Solution (NIS): Worst observed performance.
3. Separation Measures: The Euclidean distance from PIS (S_i^+) and NIS (S_i^-) was calculated for each experimental run.
5. Ranking: Experiments were ranked based on C_i^+ values in descending order.

5. Statistical Validation using ANOVA

To verify the statistical significance of the experimental results and identify influential parameters, an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted on the Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+). The ANOVA results indicated:

- Feed rate (F) and Flow rate (Q) were highly significant ($p = 0.000$), meaning they strongly influenced overall performance.
- Electrolyte concentration (C) showed a minor independent effect but interacted significantly with flow rate ($Q \times C$).

6. Integration and Interpretation

By integrating Taguchi DOE, Entropy weighting, and TOPSIS ranking, the research successfully linked experimental observations to quantitative optimization. The hybrid approach ensures:

- Objective weighting of conflicting performance criteria.
- Statistically validated parameter interactions.
- A unified ranking system providing a clear optimal solution.

This methodology demonstrates a multi-response optimization model that can be extended to other machining processes or materials. It ensures improved accuracy, reduced experimental effort, and reproducibility of results — key requirements in industrial decision-making and quality control.

7. Summary of Methodology Workflow

1. Selection of Material and Process: Inconel 625 and ECDM process chosen for their industrial relevance and machining difficulty.
2. Experimental Design: Taguchi L27 orthogonal array established to cover all variable combinations.
3. Data Collection: MRR, Ra, OC, CE, and PE measured using precision instruments.
4. Normalization and Entropy Analysis: Data standardized; weights assigned objectively.
5. TOPSIS Ranking: Computation of PIS, NIS, Si^+ , Si^- , and Ci^+ to identify the best alternative.
6. ANOVA Validation: Statistical confirmation of significant factors and regression accuracy.
7. Result Synthesis: Integration of findings for optimal machining parameter configuration.

This comprehensive methodology effectively combines experimental precision and analytical rigor. The Taguchi–Entropy–TOPSIS hybrid system provides a scientific framework to analyze complex ECDM processes involving multiple interacting variables. The statistical validation through ANOVA ensures reliability, while the entropy-based weighting eliminates subjectivity, leading to an unbiased optimization of process parameters. Ultimately, this methodological approach establishes a repeatable, data-driven pathway to achieve superior machining performance for hard-to-cut super alloys like Inconel 625.

3. Experimental description

In this study, experiments were planned using Taguchi’s design approach and conducted using the ELECHEM TECHNIK electrochemical machine. The setup for conducting the electrochemical drilling is exhibited in Figure 4.1. The ECM setup comprises the machining chamber, control panel, and pump for the circulation of electrolyte, and is designed to perform machining at 24V (Constant). The workpiece is secured in the vice located within the chamber, and the tool is secured with the main screw. The stepper motor is used to drive the main screw. A current-sensing circuit is coupled to avoid a short circuit. If the current exceeds the limit, a signal is sent to the circuit of the stepper motor controller, which prevents the downward motion of the tool. An electrolyte solution is allowed to pass through the internal hole of the electrode. Sodium chloride (NaCl) has been used as an electrolyte solution for conducting the experiments, and it was allowed to flow through the hollow-shaped electrode for the removal of material.

Figure 1: Experimental Setup for Electrochemical Drilling

Work material: Inconel 625 is a corrosion-resistant material to aggressive media and is considered a work material under this investigation. The superior and versatile corrosive resistance of Inconel 625 makes it important in the application of this material in chemical processing industries and reactor core components in nuclear water reactors, due to its strength, superior property of corrosion resistance, and resistance to stress

cracking. The chemical composition of Inconel 625 is exhibited in Table

Table 1. Chemical Composition of INCONEL 625

Element	Fe	Cr	Si	Mo	Mn	C	Ni
Wt. %	5	20-23	0.50	8-10	0.50	0.10	balance

Design of Experiments: The independent variables considered for machining of Inconel 625 are electrode feed rate, discharge rate of electrolyte, and concentration % of electrolyte. The independent variables, levels, and their range of values are specified in Table 4.2. Trials were devised by employing Taguchi’s experimental design approach. The electrochemical drilling process is carried out to make a through hole of diameter 6mm (Fig.4.2) according to the L27 orthogonal array as presented in Table

Table 2. Input Process Parameters with their Levels for ECD of Inconel 625

Factor	Process Parameter	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
F	Feed rate of electrode (mm/min)	0.15	0.2	0.25
Q	Discharge rate of Electrolyte (lit/min)	0.5	0.75	1
C	Concentration of Electrolyte (%)	10	15	20

Figure 2. Electrochemical drill Hole on INCONEL 625

Table 3. L27 Orthogonal Array

Exp No.	F	Q	C
1	0.15	0.5	10
2	0.15	0.5	15
3	0.15	0.5	20
4	0.15	0.75	10
5	0.15	0.75	15
6	0.15	0.75	20
7	0.15	1	10
8	0.15	1	15
9	0.15	1	20
10	0.2	0.5	10
11	0.2	0.5	15
12	0.2	0.5	20
13	0.2	0.75	10
14	0.2	0.75	15
15	0.2	0.75	20
16	0.2	1	10
17	0.2	1	15

18	0.2	1	20
19	0.25	0.5	10
20	0.25	0.5	15
21	0.25	0.5	20
22	0.25	0.75	10
23	0.25	0.75	15
24	0.25	0.75	20
25	0.25	1	10
26	0.25	1	15
27	0.25	1	20

Measuring the ECD Responses

The machined workpiece with 27 designed experiments is shown in Figure 4.3. The experimental responses of Material Removal Rate (MRR), Surface Roughness (R_a), Overcut (OC), Circularity error (CE), and Perpendicularity Error (PE) for each trial are measured by using various equipment.

Figure 3. Machined INCONEL 625 Plate

The material removal rate is calculated as the ratio of weight loss to the machining time in gm/min. Surface roughness (R_a) is evaluated in μm by the Kosaka make Surf coder SE1200 model with a resolution of $0.08 \mu\text{m}$. The circularity and Perpendicularity error are measured by Helmel make Co-ordinate measuring machine (CMM), model 216-142.

4. Results and Analysis

The present work analyses the Electrochemical Machining (ECM) of Inconel 625, a strong nickel-based superalloy, focusing on how electrode feed rate (F), electrode discharge rate (Q), and electrolyte concentration % (C) impact its performance characteristics. The effectiveness of the drilling process was measured using several output features such as Material Removal Rate (MRR), Surface Roughness (R_a), Overcut (OC), Circularity Error (CE), and Perpendicularity Error (PE), with the experimental data compiled into a vector decision matrix.

Table 1. Decision Matrix of the Experimental Results

S.No.	MRR (g/min)	R_a (μm)	OC (mm)	CE (mm)	PE (mm)
1	0.0638	0.42	0.365	0.186	0.129
2	0.0709	0.38	0.356	0.125	0.122
3	0.0804	0.35	0.352	0.092	0.126
4	0.072	0.49	0.352	0.267	0.125
5	0.0858	0.46	0.388	0.251	0.121
6	0.1021	0.44	0.429	0.263	0.127
7	0.0637	0.59	0.531	0.246	0.216
8	0.0842	0.57	0.612	0.276	0.214
9	0.1072	0.56	0.697	0.333	0.221
10	0.0902	0.37	0.249	0.035	0.087

11	0.0985	0.33	0.228	0.075	0.075
12	0.1094	0.3	0.211	0.088	0.073
13	0.0984	0.43	0.143	0.075	0.057
14	0.1135	0.41	0.167	0.078	0.047
15	0.1311	0.38	0.195	0.111	0.047
16	0.09	0.53	0.229	0.083	0.121
17	0.1118	0.51	0.298	0.132	0.113
18	0.1361	0.5	0.37	0.209	0.115
19	0.1211	0.32	0.256	0.241	0.212
20	0.1308	0.28	0.222	0.262	0.194
21	0.143	0.24	0.193	0.255	0.186
22	0.1293	0.37	0.057	0.104	0.155
23	0.1457	0.35	0.068	0.079	0.138
24	0.1647	0.32	0.084	0.027	0.133
25	0.1209	0.46	0.049	0.068	0.192
26	0.1441	0.45	0.105	0.014	0.177
27	0.1697	0.43	0.166	0.098	0.173

1. Entropy Weights Measurement for the Responses

The measurement of entropy weights is an objective method used to determine the importance of evaluating indicators. This approach quantifies the amount of information contained within a decision matrix.

Table 2. Entropy Indices for ECM Responses

S.No.	MRR	R _a	OC	CE	PE
1	-0.0823	-0.1228	-0.1488	-0.1409	-0.1171
2	-0.0890	-0.1145	-0.1463	-0.1069	-0.1126
3	-0.0975	-0.1080	-0.1452	-0.0856	-0.1152
4	-0.0900	-0.1366	-0.1452	-0.1786	-0.1145
5	-0.1022	-0.1308	-0.1550	-0.1717	-0.1119
6	-0.1156	-0.1269	-0.1655	-0.1769	-0.1158
7	-0.0822	-0.1547	-0.1895	-0.1695	-0.1660
8	-0.1008	-0.1512	-0.2066	-0.1824	-0.1650
9	-0.1197	-0.1494	-0.2230	-0.2047	-0.1684
10	-0.1059	-0.1124	-0.1144	-0.0409	-0.0882
11	-0.1127	-0.1036	-0.1075	-0.0736	-0.0791
12	-0.1214	-0.0967	-0.1017	-0.0829	-0.0775
13	-0.1127	-0.1248	-0.0765	-0.0736	-0.0643
14	-0.1245	-0.1208	-0.0858	-0.0757	-0.0555
15	-0.1375	-0.1145	-0.0961	-0.0982	-0.0555
16	-0.1057	-0.1440	-0.1078	-0.0793	-0.1119
17	-0.1232	-0.1403	-0.1297	-0.1111	-0.1066

18	-0.1410	-0.1385	-0.1502	-0.1524	-0.1080
19	-0.1302	-0.1013	-0.1167	-0.1673	-0.1640
20	-0.1373	-0.0920	-0.1055	-0.1765	-0.1547
21	-0.1458	-0.0821	-0.0954	-0.1735	-0.1504
22	-0.1362	-0.1124	-0.0376	-0.0937	-0.1330
23	-0.1476	-0.1080	-0.0432	-0.0765	-0.1228
24	-0.1601	-0.1013	-0.0510	-0.0333	-0.1196
25	-0.1301	-0.1308	-0.0333	-0.0683	-0.1536
26	-0.1465	-0.1288	-0.0606	-0.0195	-0.1455
27	-0.1632	-0.1248	-0.0854	-0.0897	-0.1433
e_j	0.9894	0.9928	0.9477	0.9415	0.9771
d_j	0.0106	0.0072	0.0523	0.0585	0.0229
W_j	0.0749	0.0475	0.3451	0.3859	0.1515

Normalization of the decision matrix response values is the next crucial step in the entropy weight method. After normalizing the responses using equation 3.2, the index entropy is calculated to eliminate undifferentiated indices by using equations 3.3 and 3.4, respectively. Subsequently, the evaluation index is graded, and both inner and outer weights of the evaluation index are calculated before determining the final sedimentation criticality by employing equations 3.5 and 3.6. The entropy indices obtained for the alternatives are given in Table 5.2. The corresponding weightages for the individual ECM responses are found as W_{MRR} :0.0749, W_{Ra} :0.0475, W_{OC} :0.3451, W_{CE} :0.3859, and W_{PE} :0.1515, respectively.

2. TOPSIS Optimization

Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) is a popular multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) method used to select the best alternative from a set of options. It works on the principle of choosing the alternative that is closest to the ideal solution and farthest from the negative-ideal solution.

In the TOPSIS procedure, normalization is a crucial step used to convert the decision matrix into a comparable scale, since the criteria values often have different units and magnitudes. This is typically done by dividing each criterion value by the square root of the sum of squares of that criterion column, making all values dimensionless and ranging proportionally within a uniform scale.

Table 3. Normalization (r_{ij}) Values of the Responses

S.No.	MRR	R_a	OC	CE	PE
1	0.1076	0.1898	0.2215	0.2029	0.1697
2	0.1196	0.1717	0.2160	0.1364	0.1605
3	0.1356	0.1581	0.2136	0.1004	0.1657
4	0.1215	0.2214	0.2136	0.2913	0.1644
5	0.1448	0.2078	0.2354	0.2738	0.1592
6	0.1723	0.1988	0.2603	0.2869	0.1671
7	0.1075	0.2666	0.3222	0.2684	0.2841
8	0.1421	0.2575	0.3714	0.3011	0.2815
9	0.1809	0.2530	0.4230	0.3633	0.2907
10	0.1522	0.1672	0.1511	0.0382	0.1144
11	0.1662	0.1491	0.1384	0.0818	0.0987

12	0.1846	0.1355	0.1280	0.0960	0.0960
13	0.1660	0.1943	0.0868	0.0818	0.0750
14	0.1915	0.1852	0.1013	0.0851	0.0618
15	0.2212	0.1717	0.1183	0.1211	0.0618
16	0.1518	0.2395	0.1390	0.0905	0.1592
17	0.1886	0.2304	0.1808	0.1440	0.1486
18	0.2296	0.2259	0.2245	0.2280	0.1513
19	0.2043	0.1446	0.1553	0.2629	0.2789
20	0.2207	0.1265	0.1347	0.2858	0.2552
21	0.2413	0.1084	0.1171	0.2782	0.2447
22	0.2181	0.1672	0.0346	0.1135	0.2039
23	0.2458	0.1581	0.0413	0.0862	0.1815
24	0.2779	0.1446	0.0510	0.0295	0.1749
25	0.2040	0.2078	0.0297	0.0742	0.2526
26	0.2431	0.2033	0.0637	0.0153	0.2328
27	0.2863	0.1943	0.1007	0.1069	0.2276

The weighted normalization step follows the normalization process to incorporate the relative importance of each criterion into the decision matrix. After normalizing the values, each criterion is multiplied by its assigned weight, which reflects its priority or contribution in the decision-making process. Weighted normalization ensures that the preferences of decision-makers are integrated, balances the influence of each attribute according to its relevance, and provides a realistic evaluation framework.

Table 4. Weighted Normalized (V_{ij}) Decision Matrix

S.No.	MRR	R_a	OC	CE	PE
1	0.0081	0.0090	0.0764	0.0783	0.0257
2	0.0090	0.0082	0.0746	0.0526	0.0243
3	0.0102	0.0075	0.0737	0.0387	0.0251
4	0.0091	0.0105	0.0737	0.1124	0.0249
5	0.0108	0.0099	0.0813	0.1057	0.0241
6	0.0129	0.0094	0.0898	0.1107	0.0253
7	0.0080	0.0127	0.1112	0.1036	0.0430
8	0.0106	0.0122	0.1282	0.1162	0.0426
9	0.0135	0.0120	0.1460	0.1402	0.0440
10	0.0114	0.0079	0.0521	0.0147	0.0173
11	0.0124	0.0071	0.0477	0.0316	0.0149
12	0.0138	0.0064	0.0442	0.0370	0.0145
13	0.0124	0.0092	0.0299	0.0316	0.0114

14	0.0143	0.0088	0.0350	0.0328	0.0094
15	0.0166	0.0082	0.0408	0.0467	0.0094
16	0.0114	0.0114	0.0480	0.0349	0.0241
17	0.0141	0.0109	0.0624	0.0556	0.0225
18	0.0172	0.0107	0.0775	0.0880	0.0229
19	0.0153	0.0069	0.0536	0.1015	0.0422
20	0.0165	0.0060	0.0465	0.1103	0.0387
21	0.0181	0.0052	0.0404	0.1073	0.0371
22	0.0163	0.0079	0.0119	0.0438	0.0309
23	0.0184	0.0075	0.0142	0.0333	0.0275
24	0.0208	0.0069	0.0176	0.0114	0.0265
25	0.0153	0.0099	0.0103	0.0286	0.0383
26	0.0182	0.0097	0.0220	0.0059	0.0353
27	0.0214	0.0092	0.0348	0.0413	0.0345

In the TOPSIS procedure, after weighted normalization, the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) are identified, where PIS represents the best possible values (maximum benefit or minimum cost) and NIS represents the worst values for each criterion. The identified values of PIS and NIS for the responses from the weighted normalized matrix and using equations 3.8 and 3.9

Table 5. PIS and NIS Values for the Responses

	MRR	R _a	OC	CE	PE
PIS	0.0214	0.0052	0.0103	0.0059	0.0094
NIS	0.008	0.0127	0.146	0.1402	0.044

Once ideal solutions are defined, the separation measures are calculated by determining the Euclidean distance of each alternative from both the PIS and the NIS using equations 3.10 and 3.11, respectively. These distances reflect how close or far each alternative is from the ideal and worst scenarios. The closeness coefficient (CC) is then computed as the ratio of an alternative’s distance from NIS to the total distance from both PIS and NIS, as given in equation 3.12. This coefficient, ranging between 0 and 1, indicates the relative closeness of each option to the ideal solution. The importance of this step lies in its ability to rank alternatives objectively by quantifying their proximity to the optimal choice, ensuring a rational, transparent, and consistent decision-making outcome in TOPSIS optimization.

Table 6. Separation Measures (S_i⁺, S_i⁻) and Closeness Coefficient (C_i⁺) Values for the Alternatives

S.No.	S _i ⁺	S _i ⁻	C _i ⁺
1	0.1004	0.0950	0.4862
2	0.0818	0.1148	0.5839
3	0.0740	0.1261	0.6302
4	0.1256	0.0798	0.3885
5	0.1238	0.0761	0.3807
6	0.1329	0.0664	0.3332
7	0.1452	0.0505	0.2582
8	0.1653	0.0301	0.1539
9	0.1943	0.0056	0.0280

10	0.0447	0.1590	0.7805
11	0.0466	0.1495	0.7622
12	0.0469	0.1481	0.7594
13	0.0338	0.1624	0.8275
14	0.0374	0.1585	0.8091
15	0.0513	0.1452	0.7390
16	0.0512	0.1453	0.7396
17	0.0738	0.1210	0.6214
18	0.1072	0.0892	0.4542
19	0.1101	0.1006	0.4775
20	0.1144	0.1046	0.4776
21	0.1094	0.1115	0.5047
22	0.0440	0.1659	0.7906
23	0.0333	0.1709	0.8371
24	0.0195	0.1833	0.9040
25	0.0375	0.1760	0.8242
26	0.0289	0.1833	0.8638
27	0.0499	0.1498	0.7500

The response indicates the influence of the feed rate of electrode (F), discharge rate of electrolyte (Q), and electrolyte concentration (C) on the relative closeness coefficient (C_i^+) values obtained from the TOPSIS optimization. Among the parameters, the feed rate of the electrode (F) shows the highest Delta value (8.174), meaning it has the most significant effect on C_i^+ . This suggests that variation in feed rate strongly impacts the closeness coefficient and thereby plays a dominant role in achieving optimal machining performance. The discharge rate of electrolyte (Q) has a moderate effect with a Delta value of 4.602, ranking second in influence. Meanwhile, the electrolyte concentration (C) shows the least effect (Delta = 2.557), indicating that changes in concentration contribute less to the variation in C_i^+ compared to F and Q. Overall, the results highlight that controlling the feed rate is critical for improving the relative closeness to the ideal solution, while Q has a moderate role and C exerts the least influence on the optimization outcome.

Table 7. Response Table for S/N Ratios for Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+)

Level	F	Q	C
1	-11.131	-4.514	-4.755
2	-2.958	-4.080	-5.209
3	-3.188	-8.683	-7.313
Delta	8.174	4.602	2.557
Rank	1	2	3

The main-effect plots of signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios for the closeness coefficient (C_i^+), with three panels for factors F, Q, and C across their tested levels; each panel plots mean S/N ratio on the vertical axis (higher is better, dashed reference line indicates overall mean) against factor levels on the horizontal axis, so the slope and separation of the connected points reveal each factor's influence on S/N.

For factor F (left panel, levels 0.15, 0.20, 0.25) the S/N ratio is lowest at 0.15 mm/min and increases sharply to a peak at 0.20 mm/min then slightly drops at 0.25 mm/min, indicating at 0.20 mm/min feed rate of electrode (F) gives the most robust (highest S/N) closeness coefficient and that F has a strong non-linear effect. For Q (middle panel, levels 0.5, 0.75, 1.0) S/N is moderate at 0.5 lit/min, rises a bit at 0.75 lit/min and then falls substantially at 1.0 lit/min, showing the best robustness near at

0.75 lit/min discharge rate of electrolyte and a detrimental effect at the highest Q. For C (right panel, levels 10, 15, 20) S/N declines steadily as C increases, so the smallest tested C (10%) produces the highest S/N and greater C values reduce robustness. Overall, the plot identifies the best settings for maximizing the S/N of the closeness coefficient (C_i^+), as the feed rate of electrode (F) \approx 0.20 mm/min, discharge rate of electrolyte (Q) \approx 0.75 lit/min, and electrolyte concentration % (C) \approx 10%, respectively. Overall, it is found that F and Q have nonmonotonic effects, while C shows a clear monotonic decrease, and suggests prioritizing changes in F and Q around their moderate levels and keeping C low to improve the closeness coefficient's signal-to-noise (S/N) performance.

Figure 4. Main effect Plots for S/N Ratios of Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+)

The ANOVA table 5.8 shows that a statistical model was built to predict the Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+) using three factors of electrode feed rate (F), electrode discharge rate (Q), and electrolyte concentration % (C). The results indicate the model is highly effective ($P=0.000$). The most influential factors are F ($F = 116.44, P = 0.000$) and Q ($F = 6.78, P = 0.019$), which not only have a direct impact but also a curved (nonlinear) relationship with the outcome, for $F \times F$ ($F = 41.96, P = 0.000$) and $Q \times Q$ ($F = 13.28, P = 0.002$) respectively. Furthermore, there are significant interaction effects, meaning the influence of one factor depends on the level of another. Specifically, the interaction between F and Q ($F = 86.16, P = 0.000$) is very strong, and the one between Q and C ($F = 9.41, P = 0.007$) is also significant. In contrast,

factor C ($F = 2.53, P = 0.130$) by itself is not a significant predictor of the Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+).

Table 8. ANOVA Results for Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+)

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F	P
Model	9	1.34549	0.149499	30.85	0.000
Linear	3	0.60936	0.203120	41.92	0.000
F	1	0.56423	0.564233	116.44	0.000
Q	1	0.03285	0.032850	6.78	0.019
C	1	0.01228	0.012276	2.53	0.130
Square	3	0.26939	0.089797	18.53	0.000
FxF	1	0.20335	0.203346	41.96	0.000
QxQ	1	0.06433	0.064333	13.28	0.002
CxC	1	0.00171	0.001711	0.35	0.560
2-way Interaction	3	0.46674	0.155580	32.11	0.000
FxQ	1	0.41753	0.417527	86.16	0.000
FxC	1	0.00360	0.003603	0.74	0.401
QxC	1	0.04561	0.045610	9.41	0.007
Error	17	0.08238	0.004846		

Total	26	1.42787		
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- $S = 0.0696125$, $R^2 = 94.23\%$, $R^2(\text{Adj}) = 91.18\%$, $R^2(\text{Pred}) = 84.09\%$

Figure 5. Residual plots for Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+)

The residual plots shown in Figure 5.2 are diagnostic tools used to verify the integrity of the statistical model for the Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+). Each plot checks a specific assumption. The Normal Probability Plot and the Histogram both confirm that the errors are normally distributed, as the data points closely follow the straight line and the bars form a bell-like shape. The Residuals Versus Fits plot shows a random scatter of points around the central zero line, indicating that the errors have a constant variance and the model hasn't missed any underlying patterns. Finally, the Residuals Versus Order plot displays a random pattern, confirming that the errors are independent and not influenced by the order in which the data was collected. The overall conclusion from these four plots is that the model is statistically valid and reliable. The errors behave as expected for a well-fitted model, which gives us confidence in the results, such as the significance of factors identified in the ANOVA analysis.

5. Conclusions and Future Scope

The current research work details the multi-objective optimization of electrochemical drilling of Inconel 625 using the Taguchi-based Entropy-TOPSIS technique. The following conclusions were drawn from this experimental research. Besides the material removal rate and surface roughness, the geometric measures, such as overcut, form, and orientation tolerance errors, are included for performance measures, which makes the investigation unique.

- The multi-response optimization through the proposed method yielded a single optimal solution for all the responses considered, as Feed rate at 0.20 mm/min, flow rate at 0.75 lit/min, and Electrolyte concentration at 10% produce better multi-performance machining characteristics.
- From Taguchi results, it is found that feed rate (F) and flow rate (Q) have nonmonotonic effects, while Electrolyte concentration % (C) shows a clear monotonic decrease, and suggests prioritizing changes in F and Q around their moderate levels and keeping C low to improve the closeness coefficient's signal-to-noise (S/N) performance.
- ANOVA results showed that the statistical model built to predict the Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+) is highly effective ($P=0.000$).
- The most influential factors are F ($F = 116.44$, $P = 0.000$) and Q ($F = 6.78$, $P = 0.019$), which not only have a direct impact but also a curved (non-linear) relationship with the outcome.
- The interaction effects between F and Q ($F = 86.16$, $P = 0.000$) are very strong, and the one between Q and C ($F = 9.41$, $P = 0.007$) is also significant.
- Factor C ($F = 2.53$, $P = 0.130$) by itself is not a significant predictor of the Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+).

- The regression model built for Closeness Coefficient (C_i^+) is more accurate and adequate, as its coefficient determination values are obtained as $R^2 = 94.23\%$, and $R^2(\text{Adj}) = 91.18\%$ respectively.
- The proposed Taguchi-based Entropy-TOPSIS approach is appropriate to establish the best possible solution for the set of input process variables, depending upon the desired multiple performance characteristics.

FUTURE SCOPE

The present work can be further extended by experimenting with different work materials and varying the controllable process parameters. Comparative studies may also be carried out using other multi-objective optimization techniques to validate and enhance the findings. Additionally, detailed microstructural analysis of the machined or drilled surfaces can be performed to gain deeper insights into surface integrity and improve quality assessment.

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